

The MOLAB transnational access for an *in situ* investigation of the Hunt frieze of the tomb of Philip II at Aigai (Vergina, Greece)

Michela Botticelli,(1,2) Eva Luna Ravan,(1,2) Danilo Paolo Pavone,(1,2) Claudia Caliri,(1,2) Francesco Paolo Romano,(1,2), Brenda Doherty,(3) Francesca Sabatini,(3) Fauzia Albertin,(3) Francesca Rosi,(3) Aldo Romani,(4) Sotiria Kogou,(5) Florence Liggins,(5) Chi Shing Cheung,(5) Haida Liang,(5), Nikoletta-Kanella Kladouri,(6) Kalliopi Tsampa, (6) Andreas Germanos Karydas,(6) Anastasia Georgiadou,(7) and Hariclia Brecolaki,(8)

(1) Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale (CNR- ISPC), Catania, Italy

(2) Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, Laboratori Nazionali del Sud (INFN-LNS), Catania, Italy

(3) Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche (CNR-SCITEC), Perugia, Italy

(4) Centro di Eccellenza SMAArt, Dipartimento di Chimica Biologia e Biotecnologie dell'Università di Perugia, Perugia, Italy

(5) Imaging & Sensing for Archaeology, Art History & Conservation (ISAAC) Laboratory, School of Science and Technology, Nottingham Trent University, Nottingham, U.K.

(6) Institute of Nuclear and Particle Physics, NCSR "Demokritos", Agia Paraskevi, Attiki, Greece

(7) Greek ministry of Culture, Ephorate of Antiquities of Emathia, Greece

(8) Institute of Historical Research, National Hellenic Research Foundation, Athens, Greece

Funerary paintings from ancient Macedonia produced under the reign of Philip II and Alexander the Great offer the most significant insights into monumental painting during the late Classical and early Hellenistic period. On the large-scale compositions decorating the façades and the interiors of Macedonian tombs it is possible to investigate the ancient painters' techniques and to explore the themes of a local funerary iconography. A recent analytical campaign by the MOLAB facilities within the IPERION HS consortium as part of the research project REVIS, funded by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation, assisted in the characterization of the largest and most famous Classical painting, the Hunt frieze of the façade of the Tomb of Philip II at ancient Aigai (Vergina), NE Greece, providing non-invasive mobile in-situ analyses: MA-XRF and XRD, single-point reflection spectroscopy in the Vis-NIR-SWIR and mid-IR ranges, Vis-NIR (400-1000nm) reflectance spectral imaging (RSI) at close range on scaffolding platform and remote sensing techniques at ~10m from the ground such as VIS-SWIR (400-2500 nm) RSI, laser induced fluorescence (LIF) spectral imaging and Raman spectroscopy.

MA-XRF imaging was used to infer elemental content and spatial distribution of the original inorganic materials, further characterized by XRD point analysis and mapping and complemented by single point external reflection FTIR and Vis-NIR-SWIR. Results confirm the use of a rich gamut of pigments and suggest the presence of unusual Cu,As-based minerals with greenish hues. MA-XRF imaging evidenced iconographic details no longer visible to the naked eye, due to the poor state of preservation and the significant losses of the pictorial layers, dramatically affecting the legibility of the painting. The combination of VIS-NIR-RSI with FTIR gave indications on the ongoing deterioration mechanisms and contributed to the identification of organic materials. Remote imaging/sensing techniques supported the identification of chemical compounds on the whole frieze.